

Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric

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Abstract

Textile science of chemical processing encompass diverse disciplines and areas of expertise. In the present scenario of industrial consciousness, integration in all aspects of textile wet processing is commercial ultimatum where everyone is repeatedly querying to textile scientist. The present research on combined dyeing and finishing is prime of them. Combined dyeing and finishing offer considerable economy in operating costs because of the simplicity of the operations. This research work was proceeded to study the feasibility of combined dyeing and multifinishing (fragrance, water repellency, antcrease, and crease recovery) in one step to reduce processing costs like as time saving, heat energy saving, water, low vapour-gas-emission, low labour cost, environment-friendly and also worked on to develop and optimize durable fragrance finishing for cotton textiles which may be an alternative invention of artificial application of perfume on textile substrate named as cosmetic finishing. Beta cyclodextrin, Dextrin and Dimethylol Dihydroxy Ethylene Urea (DMDHEU) were applied for reactive dyeing and finishing of cotton fabric in conventional double stage exhaust and combined pad-dry-cure method where combined method of dyeing and finishing with beta cyclodextrin showed higher color strength (K/S value), dry crease recovery angle, tensile strength than using double stage method. As fragrance chemical: synthetic fragrance (Jasmine), Rose oil and Patchouli oil were used with beta cyclodextrin and without beta cyclodextrin. Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine) with beta cyclodextrin showed high level of fragrance intensity in combined dyeing and finishing than double stage method. Fragrance intensity was tested by human sensorial evaluation was found 10% after 70 days without washing and 30% retained after five time washing.

Keywords

Dyeing, Finishing, Beta Cyclodextrin, Aroma finish, Microencapsulation, Emulsion.

Cite

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Introduction

β -cyclodextrin is the aromatherapeutic textile as host molecule, because it exhibits qualities which are beneficial for the human body. β -cyclodextrins molecules are capable of forming inclusion compounds with fragrances that fit into the cone-shaped hydrophobic cavity. As a result, the release-fragrance rates are greatly decreased. There are many possibilities for the development of new textile products with advanced properties based on β -cyclodextrin. Microencapsulation technology is an effective technique used to control the release properties of active ingredients that prolong the functionality of cosmetic textiles. Focusing on the field of cosmetic textiles, the major interest in microencapsulation is currently in the application of attractive fragrances, vitamins, essential oils, skin moisturizing agents, skin cooling agents etc. The investigation ⁽¹⁾ of US retail sales of home fragrance shows that sales increased 9.7 percent, from \$1.35 billion in 1995 to \$1.96 billion in 1999. Pleasure and enjoyment⁽²⁾ on the one hand, is about daring to be different, but also about forgetting stress. Excitement and active wear is a form of communication. ⁽³⁾ The scents of lavender, rose, citrus or vanilla were encapsulated into cotton fabrics⁽²⁵⁾, which proved a good way to meet important psychological and emotional needs, as well as those of a purely physical and sensorial nature aromatherapy was coined in the late 1920s by the French cosmetic chemist R.M. Gattefosse, who noticed the excellent antiseptic proper-ties and skin permeability of essential oils. Dr. Charles Tomasino ⁽⁴⁾ reviewed that natural starches are not very soluble in cold water and Dextrin⁽⁵⁾ has OH group and Cyclodextrins ^(24, 25) are cyclic oligosaccharides containing six, seven eight, nine ten, eleven, twelve, thirteen 1,4-linked glycopyranose units with a

hydrophilic hydroxyl group on their outer surface and a hydrophobic cavity in the center. The general features of β -cyclodextrin⁽⁷⁾ that β -cyclodextrin can act as a host for various guest molecules and Devinderkaur and Neelam Grewal⁽⁶⁾ reviewed that the cyclodextrin capacity to form inclusion complexes is known for a long time. Cyclodextrins^(8,16) clamped on cellulose do not affect the cellulose's properties and fragrance was encapsulated with beta cyclodextrin and perfume retention onto the fabric although fragrance compound⁽¹⁷⁾ and the essential oil are volatile substances and the mechanism of microencapsulation⁽¹⁹⁾ was core material + wall shell = controlled release. J. Kotch⁽⁹⁾ reviewed that Complexed with cyclodextrin, perfumes are stable and B. Martel and et.al.⁽¹⁰⁾ reviewed that Permanent fixation of cyclodextrins onto textiles. J.-P. Moldenhauer⁽¹¹⁾ found that β -cyclodextrin is a reactive cyclodextrin derivative that can be covalently fixed to nucleophilic substrates by a substitution reaction carried out by the usual finishing procedure. Both alkaline and acidic methods⁽¹²⁾ for MCT- β -cyclodextrin finishes have been developed to suit customers. Underwear, gloves, socks⁽¹³⁾ can be loaded with the necessary antifungal, antihistaminic, and anti-inflammatory agents. Flowers, leaves and fruit used as ingredients^(14, 15, 16) of perfume and Only a few molecules⁽¹⁴⁾ are necessary for us to experience or identify scents, and characteristically, the worse a smell is, the less it takes to notice it. The most commonly used microencapsulation processes⁽²⁰⁾, including Complex Coacervation, Polymer-Polymer Incompatibility, Interfacial Polymerisation and In Situ Polymerisation, Spray Drying, Centrifugal Extrusion, Air Suspension Coating, Pan Coating, and Emulsion Hardening Process and⁽²¹⁾ SEM (Scanning electron microscopy), Infra-Red (IR) Spectroscopy, Thin Layer chromatography, TLCX-ray diffractometry and Single crystal X-ray structure analysis are the important testing of microencapsulation. For micro-encapsulation⁽²³⁾ cyclodextrins are the best regarding safety to the human body, because β -cyclodextrin has no skin irritation, no skin sensitisation and no mutagenic effect. Detailed studies of toxicology⁽⁵⁾, mutagenicity, teratogenicity and carcinogenicity were indicated that the cyclodextrin can affect the human organism only at extremely high concentrations. Successful example of using cyclodextrin for aroma finishing⁽²²⁾ with Sensorial evaluation of scent intensity with cyclodextrin. Monochlorotriazinyl functional group⁽²⁵⁾ of reactive dye reacts with beta cyclodextrin and cotton fibre in same bath. Cotton fabric⁽²⁸⁾ was modified with beta cyclodextrin and crosslinked with citric acid and highly increased K/S value and strength. Simultaneous dyeing and finishing⁽²⁹⁾ of jute carpet backing cloth was found in dye fixation, crease recovery and reduction in moisture regain.

Materials

Plain weave 100% cotton fabric by weighting 54 GSM was purchased from Khadi Silk Imporium, Dakshinapan Market, Kolkata, India.

Chemical used	Sourcing/Company Name	Chemical used	Sourcing/Company Name
Reactive dye-Orange-CN	Dyechem international, Kolkata	Sodium carbonate	Laboratory grade
Reactive dye-Yellow-CN	Dyechem international, Kolkata	Sodium chloride	Laboratory grade
Reactive dye-Lemon Yellow-CN	Dyechem international, Kolkata	Citric acid	Laboratory grade
Beta Cyclodextrin	TCI Chemical Ltd. India	Distilled water	Laboratory grade
Dextrin	Laboratory grade	Fragrance Chemical used	Sourcing/Company Name
Dimethyl dihydroxy ethylene urea (DMDHEU)	Clarient, India	Synthetic fragrance chemical	LN chemical industries ltd, Mumbai, India
Polyethylene Glycol	Laboratory grade	Rose Oil	Chemical supplier, kolkata, India
Sodium hypophosphite	Laboratory grade	Pachouli oil	Govt. Emitine factory, Darjeeling, West Bengal, India

Double stage dyeing and finishing:

In double stage dyeing and finishing, bleached cotton fabric was dyed with conventional exhaust method of reactive dyeing and ready dyed fabric was finished by applying same finishing chemical (without dye only) of combined dyeing and finishing with pad (80%)-dry (100°C) –cure (150°C) method. Similarly, also observed the effect of beta cyclodextrin for microencapsulation in double stage dyeing and multi-finishing comparing with dextrin and

DMDHEU. As cyclodextrin can bond with monochlorotriazinyl group of reactive dye⁽⁷⁾ and textile fibre, so for both double stage and combined dyeing and finishing, monochlorotriazinyl group of reactive dye has been used in this project work.

Combined dyeing and multi-finishing:

Beta cyclodextrin was found very weak soluble in water, so polyethylene glycol was used to make highly soluble with water and fragrance chemical which created good emulsion of fragranced and beta cyclodextrin chemical. Dextrin (5%, 10%, 15%) and DMDHEU (5%, 10%, 15%) were used to compare the capability of microencapsulation of used beta cyclodextrin (5%,10%, 15%). Concentration of reactive dye-1% Citric acid -10% and sodium hypophosphite-6% were kept for all recipe in this work and fragrance chemical were kept 1% in first recipe and 1%, 2%, 3% in second recipe to know the better intensity level of fragrance as per concentration. Sodium carbonate was only used to keep pH 10-11 which created proper reaction of Beta cyclodextrin, monochlorotriazinyl group of reactive dye and cotton fibre. To make good emulsion chemical was dissolved with mixer for 5 minutes in an open biker. After visual satisfaction of mixing solution was used for combined dyeing and finishing.

Data Table-1: Effect of beta cyclodextrin for microencapsulation in combined dyeing and finishing comparing with dextrin and DMDHEU:

An Emulsifier was prepared by Polyethylene glycol & Distilled water (1:3) ⁽²²⁾							
Types of chemicals	Concentration	Reactive Lemon yellow-CN	Synthetic Fragrance	Citric Acid	Sodium Hypophospite	Emulsifier	Sodium Carbonate ⁽²⁷⁾
Beta Cyclodextrin	5% ⁽²⁴⁾	1%	1%	10% ⁽²⁶⁾	6% ⁽²⁶⁾	77%	for pH10-11
	10% ⁽²⁴⁾	1%	1%	10%	6%	72%	for pH 10-11
	15% ⁽²⁴⁾	1%	1%	10%	6%	67%	for pH 10-11
Dextrin	5%	1%	1%	10%	6%	77%	for pH 10-11
	10%	1%	1%	10%	6%	72%	for pH 10-11
	15%	1%	1%	10%	6%	67%	for pH 10-11
DMDHEU	5%	1%	1%	10%	6%	77%	for pH 10-11
	10%	1%	1%	10%	6%	72%	for pH 10-11
	15%	1%	1%	10%	6%	67%	for pH 10-11

Table 1, dyeing and Fragrance intensity were found comparatively better for the recipe of beta cyclodextrin. So further research was proceeded by using beta cyclodextrin.

Data Table-02: Effect of fragrance and beta cyclodextrin in combined dyeing and finishing

An Emulsifier was prepared by Polyethylene glycol & Distilled water (1:3) ⁽²²⁾							
Types of fragrance	Fragrance concentration	Dye lemon yellow CN	Beta Cyclodextrin	Emulsifier	Citric acid	Sodium hypophosphite	Sodium carbonate ⁽²⁷⁾
Synthetic (Jasmine)	1%	1%	10%	72%	10% ⁽²⁵⁾	6% ⁽²⁵⁾	For pH 10-11
	2%	1%	10%	71%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
	3%	1%	10%	70%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
Rose oil	1%	1%	10%	72%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
	2%	1%	10%	71%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
	3%	1%	10%	70%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
Pachouli oil	1%	1%	10%	72%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
	2%	1%	10%	71%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
	3%	1%	10%	70%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine)	1%	1%	0%	72%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
	2%	1%	0%	71%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
	3%	1%	0%	70%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11

Rose oil	1%	1%	0%	72%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
	2%	1%	0%	71%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
	3%	1%	0%	70%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
Pachouli oil	1%	1%	0%	72%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
	2%	1%	0%	71%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11
	3%	1%	0%	70%	10%	6%	For pH 10-11

Table 2, dyeing and fragrance intensity were found comparatively better for synthetic fragrance, so further research was proceeded by using synthetic fragrance.

Probable reaction in combined dyeing and finishing where monochlorotriazinyl group of reactive dye is making covalent bond with beta cyclodextrin and OH group of cotton fibre:

Results and discussion

Research work on combined dyeing and finishing where successfully found logical result which is more beneficial comparing to double stage dyeing and finishing in each and every point of view.

1. Reactive dyes are the most popular application class used to dye cellulose fibres. It forms covalent bond with cellulose. Due to the strong primary bonding between dyes and fibres, it possessed high level of fastness such as color fastness, water fastness and light fastness. But the fastness of color, water and wash is slightly poor than double stage dyeing and finishing (**shown in table 3**). In combined dyeing and finishing method, Beta cyclodextrin is crosslinking with fibre and increasing the affinity of dyestuff to fabric. The major drawback of reactive dyes is hydrolysis in which dye instead of reacting with fibre reacts with the hydroxide anion of the base and as a result high amount of wastage of dyestuff is occurred in conventional dyeing. But in combined dyeing and finishing with Beta cyclodextrin, hydrolysis rate of dyestuff is minimizing and wastage rate of dyestuff is very minor. So, this project work is more beneficial to minimize the wastage of dyestuff.
2. The water repellency rating analysis shows that, the beta cyclodextrin are highly improving the rating of water repellency (**shown in table-3**) of woven cotton fabric. Water repellency properties of cotton have been found better for beta cyclodextrin treatment in case of unwashed sample. Water repellency also depends on the fibre type, yarn and fabric structure.
3. Cotton is an important fibre in textiles, because of its numerous advantages. One of the main disadvantages of cotton shows crease mark after washing. On creasing the cotton fabrics, the molecular chains in the amorphous region slip past each other, breaking the weak hydrogen bonds. The stretched chains then form hydrogen bonds in the stretched places and thus the fabric holds the creases. The mechanism of the crease recovery process in cotton fibres is improving with stable cross-links so as to prevent slippage of molecular chains. In combined dyeing and finishing with beta cyclodextrin is successfully improving the dry crease recovery angle of fabric (**shown in table 03**) which is a major benefit of this project work in the field of textile chemistry.
4. Ecofriendly dyeing: Salt free dyeing and so from environmental point of view, harmful effects of high concentrated salt has been controlled.

5. Finishing with DMDHEU formaldehyde has been question mark, Beta cyclodextrin can be substituted chemical of DMDHEU. Not only that DMDHEU declines tensile strength of fabric but Beta Cyclodextrin increases the tensile strength of cotton fabric
6. Finishing with Beta Cyclodextrin, I have found good intensity of fragrance (**shown in table-03**) after five time washing & long-time duration of fragrance intensity without washing.
7. In combined dyeing and multi-finishing (water repellency, antcrease and fragrance finishing) with Beta Cyclodextrin and fragrance chemical is increasing the color strength (K/S) (**Shown in table 3**)

Data Table-03: Effect of physical properties, dyeing properties and finishing properties of double stage dyeing and finishing as well as combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric

Treatments	Tensile strength (N/M) warp, weft	(+) in strength	(-) in strength	K/S value	Color fastness rating	Light Fastness rating	Water Repellency rating	Dry crease recovery angle
Testing machine and method	<i>Instron, IS-1969-1985</i>			Macbeth 2020 plus spectrophotometer		Xenon test chamber, AATCC TM16	Sprey test AATCC Test Method 22-2010	ASTM-D-1295-67, Shirly tester
Bleached untreated cotton fabric	0.278,0.208		0.002, 0.003	0.054	-	-	0	162
Dyed cotton fabric with conventional method	0.270, 0.200		0.008, 0.008	3.001	3	3	20	180
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and beta cyclodextrin	0.276, 0.205		0.008, 0.013	2.898	4	4	70	256
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and without beta cyclodextrin	0.270, 0.195		0.004, 0.009	2.999	2	2	40	200
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and dextrin instead of B-CD	0.274, 0.199		0.018, 0.013	2.695	2	2	60	230
Double stage dyed and	0.260, 0.195	.012,.072	-	2.565	2	2	70	250

finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and DMDHEU instead of B-CD									
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and beta cyclodextrin	0.290, 0.280		0.003, 0.008	3.239	3	3	75	264	
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and without beta cyclodextrin	0.275, 0.200	0	0	3.338	2	2	50	190	
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and dextrin instead of B-CD	0.278, 0.208		0.009, 0.010	2.765	2	2	70	220	
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and DMDHEU instead of B-CD	0.269, 0.198		0.002, 0.003	2.865	2	2	70	240	

Table 3, in combined dyeing and finishing with beta cyclodextrin tensile strength, K/S value, water repellency & dry crease recovery angle was increased which creates a new platform for dyeing technology by providing more cost-effective benefits compared to double stage dyeing and finishing.

Data Table-04: Fragrance grading scale 0-100%, human sensorial evaluation after number of days without washing

Types of fragrance	Fragrance conc.	Beta Cyclodextrin	First day	10 th day	20 th day	30 th day	40 th day	50 th day	60 th day	70 th day	80 th day
Synthetic (Jasmine)	1%	10%	90%	80%	80%	70%	70%	30%	20%	10%	0%
	2%	10%	95%	85%	85%	80%	70%	40%	20%	10%	0%
	3%	10%	95%	85%	85%	80%	70%	40%	20%	10%	0%
Rose oil	1%	10%	50%	40%	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	55%	40%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	10%	55%	40%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	10%	85%	70%	40%	10%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	90%	70%	40%	10%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%

	3%	10%	90%	70%	40%	10%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine)	1%	0%	90%	70%	50%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	90%	70%	50%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	90%	70%	50%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Rose oil	1%	0%	90%	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	90%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	90%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	0%	90%	40%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	90%	40%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	90%	40%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Table 4, as fragrance on combined dyeing and finishing has been found higher intensity than double stage dyeing and finishing, so details study on fragrance intensity has been proceeded only for combined dyeing and finishing. Fragrance of synthetic jasmine was retained up to 70 days without washing where beta cyclodextrin was used 10% but fragrance finishing without beta cyclodextrin retained up to 30 days only.

Data Table-05: Effect of fragrance and beta cyclodextrin for finishing of ready dyed fabric combined dyeing and finishing

Types of fragrance	Fragrance conc.	Beta Cyclodextrin	Fragrance grading scale 0-100%, human sensorial evaluation after number of washing					
			Before washing	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth
Synthetic (Jasmine)	1%	10%	90%	90%	80%	60%	50%	30%
	2%	10%	95%	90%	80%	70%	60%	40%
	3%	10%	95%	90%	80%	70%	60%	40%
Rose oil	1%	10%	50%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	55%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	10%	55%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	10%	85%	50%	20%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	90%	60%	30%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	10%	90%	60%	30%	0%	0%	0%
Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine)	1%	0%	90%	60%	40%	10%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	95%	70%	90%	10%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	95%	70%	90%	10%	0%	0%
Rose oil	1%	0%	40%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	45%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	45%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	0%	85%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Table 5, as fragrance on combined dyeing and finishing has been found higher intensity than double stage dyeing and finishing, so details study on fragrance intensity has been proceeded only for combined dyeing and finishing. In combined dyeing and finishing: time, heat energy saving, water, low vapour-gas-emission, environment-friendly labour can be saved highly than double stage dyeing and finishing.

Effect of textile dye house effluent and our environment of combined dyeing and finishing

Auto-minimization of waste water damping: As my project work on combined dyeing and finishing, the use of water will minimize where there is no doubt from above discussion. So, there is no confusion to say the damping rate of waste water will reduce highly.

No Salinity in waste water: As my project work is salt free combined dyeing and finishing there is no load of salinity in waste water which not only minimizing the ETP (Effluent Treatment Plant) cost but also protect the aquatic life.

Minimization of ETP running cost: ETP running cost is about 3.00 to 3.50 for per kg finished fabric production. So, from above two point we can clearly identify that my project work is minimizing the running cost of effluent treatment plant.

Conclusion

Since 1980, when Szejtli first patented the bonding of CDs onto textile fibres, a lot of research has gone into the application of CDs. But there is still a gap between original high level basic science and commercial applications of CDs in textile sectors. From this research, it is to explore the application of cyclodextrin for the purpose of incorporating fragrance oil into cotton fabrics which will create film forming ability and at the same time increasing the K/S value of dyed fabric in combined dyeing and finishing. As 100% cotton is predominant fibre used for underwear and socks producing textiles where fragrance finishing has a great value. At last, the use of beta cyclodextrin as a binder for the application of microencapsulated fragrance oil results in high fragrance retention in 100% cotton fabrics. Thus, beta cyclodextrin with microencapsulated fragrance oil can be utilized to develop textiles to achieve the necessary fragrance finishing and beta cyclodextrin can be used in dyeing bath as auxiliaries.

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References

1. Mazzaro, D. 2000. The home fragrance market. Chemical Market Reporter, August 4:14.
2. Bartolomeo, J. Aromarama. Women's Sports & Fitness. 1999,3(11-12):84.
3. Matsushi-Shikiso Chemical Co. Ltd. Fixing Odourous to Textiles. High-Performance-Textiles. 1994(8):7-8.
4. Dr. Charles Tomasino, Dept. of textile engineering, North Carolina state university, Chemistry and technology of fabric preparation and finishing, Pages: 17, 50, 102-106, 109-114, 130,154-162, 164-170, 219.
5. David Rowe, WILEY publications, Chemistry and technology of flavours and fragrances.
6. Durable antimicrobial finishing on organic cotton by inclusion of thymol into cyclodextrin derivative, M. Sundrarajan and Rukmani, E-journal of chemistry, 2012, 9(3) 1511-1517, <http://www.ejchem.net>.
7. Application of cyclodextrines in textiles – a review, Aurelia Grigoriu and Octavian Popescu, Buletinul institutului politehnic din Iasi, Publicat de, Universitatea Tehnica "Gheorghe asachi" din Iasi, Tomul LVII (LXI), Fasc.2,2011.
8. Bushmann, H-j. Removal of Residual surfactant deposits from textile materials with the aid of cyclodextrins. Melliand Textilberchite.
9. Stabilisation and controlled release of perfume in detergents, J. Koch, in proc. 1st Int. Symp. Cyclodextrins (Ed.:J. Szejtli)Reidel, Dordrecht, 1982, P.487
10. Polycarboxylic acids as crosslinking agents for grafting cyclodextrins onto cotton and wool fabrics : study of the process parameters, B. Martel, M. Wetrowski, D. Ruffin, M. morcellet, J. Appl. Polym. Sci 2002, 83(7), 1449-1456.
11. Textile finishing with MCT-Beta cyclodextrin, J.-P. Moldenhauer, H. Reuscher, in Proc.9th Int. Symp. Cyclodextrins (1999), (Eds. J. Torres Labandeira, J.L. Vila-jato), Kluwer Academic publishers, Dordrecht,1998, pp. 161-165.
12. H.-J. Buschmann, D. Knittel, E. Schollmeyer: Use of cyclodextrins for improving waste air washers, Melliand Textil-ber.2001,

- 82(5), E94-E96, 368-370.
13. New textile applications of cyclodextrins, H.-J. Buschmann, D. Knittel, E. Schollmeyer, J. Inclusion Phenom. Macrocyclic Chem. 2001, 40(3), 169-172.
 14. Perfumed textiles, Katia Johansen, Textile society of America symposium proceedings, Paper 104 September 4-7, 2008, <http://disitalcommons.unl.edu/tsaconf/104>.
 15. Effects of fragrance on emotions: Moods and physiology, Stephen Warrenburg, International flavors and fragrances Inc, 1515 Rt. 36, Union Beach, NJ07735, USA, email: Stephen. Warrenburg @ iff.com.
 16. Aromatextiles, <http://textilelearner.blogspot.com/2013/03/aroma-textile-application-of.html#ixzz3lkzlxk00>.
 17. Shirley Institute, New finishes using microencapsulation, Textile month, 1988(5): 49-49, Mei W-P. Application of Microencapsulation, Technology in textile coloration and finishing, Journal-china-Textile-Institute.1995.5 (3):188-191.
 18. Leena Mishra, Dept. Of Fibres & Textile Processing Technology, University Of Mumbai, Institute Of Chemical Technology, MICRO ENCAPSULATION: AN OVERVIEW & IT'S APPLICATION IN TEXTILE WET PROCESSING.
 19. Development of cosmetic textiles using microencapsulation technology, S. Y. cheng, C.W.M. Yuen, C.W. Kan and K.K.L. Cheuk, RJTA Vol.12 (4) 2008.
 20. Effect of ecofriendly microencapsulated textile products in joint pain and aesthetic respondents, Devinder Kaur and Neelam Grewal, Journal of polymer and textile engineering, Vol.1, Issue 2, PP:41-45, January 2014
 21. Characterization of cyclodextrin inclusion complexes-a Review, Ramnik Singh, Nitin Bharti, Jyotsana, Madan, S.N. hiremath, Khalsa college of pharmacy, Amritsar-143302, Punjab, india, Sri Sri college of pharmacy, Badhani, Pathankot-145001(Punjab0, Pravara rural education society's college of pharmacy, Chincholi, Nashik-422101.
 22. Aromachology and its application in the textile field, C.X. Wang, Sh.L.Chen, email: Wangchaoxia@sohu.com, College of textile and garments, Southern Yangtze University, College of chemistry and Chemical engineering, Donghua University, Shanghai 200051, P.R. China
 23. Cyclodextrins and dextrans as new auxiliaries in dyeing, Buschmann, H-J, Melliand Textilberchite, 1991, 72 (12): 1012-1014.
 24. Cyclodextrin in the textile industry, Jozsef Szejtli, CYCLOLAB , Research and development laboratory ltd., Budapest, Hungary, Starch/Stärke 55, (2003) 191- 196.
 25. Application of B-cyclodextrins in textiles, Usha Rashmi Bhaskara-Amrit, Pramod B. Agrawal and Marijin M.C.G. Warmoeskerken, AUTEX Research journal, Vol.11, (4) December 2011.
 26. Imparting antimicrobial and fragrance finish on cotton using chitosan with silicon softner, Anjali Karolia, Snehal Mendapara, Indian journal of fibre and textile science, Volume-32, March-2007, PP-99-104.
 27. Synthesis of reactive fragranced entities and their application to cotton textiles, D.P. Chattopadhyay, Shweta, J.Doctor, Textiles and light industrial science and technology, Volume-2, Issue-2, April-2013.
 28. Improvement of ink jet printing performance using beta cyclodextrin on cotton fabric, Textile research journal, Manuscript ID TRJ-15-0179
 29. Simultaneous dyeing and finishing, M Kamaluddin, M E Molla, S M B Rahman, M A K Azad, H M ZakirHossain & M M U Jubayer, J Bio Sci, 7(1) (2007)68 -70

JFT-05

INTEGRATED DYEING AND COSMETIC FINISHING ON COTTON FABRIC**Md. Anowar Hossain**

*M. Tech. Student, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology,
Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta
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ABSTRACT

Textile science of chemical processing encompass diverse disciplines and areas of expertise. In the present scenario of industrial consciousness, integration in all aspects of textile wet processing is commercial ultimatum where everyone is repeatedly querying to textile scientist. The present research on combined dyeing and finishing is prime of them. Combined dyeing and finishing offers considerable economy in operating costs because of the simplicity of the operations. Project work was proceeded to study the feasibility of combined dyeing and multifinishing (fragrance, water repellency, antcrease, crease recovery) in one step to reduce process cost like as time saving , heat energy saving, water, low vapour-gas-emission, low labour cost, environment –friendly and also worked on to develop and optimize durable fragrance finishing for cotton textiles which may be an alternative invention of artificial application of perfume on textile substrate named as cosmetic finishing. Beta cyclodextrin, Dextrin and DMDHEU were applied for reactive dyeing and finishing of cotton fabric inconventional double stage exhaust and combined pad-dry-cure method where combined method of dyeing and finishing with beta cyclodextrin showed higher K/S value, dry crease recovery angle, tensile strength than using double stage method. As fragrance chemical: synthetic fragrance (Jasmine), Rose oil and Pachouli oil were used with beta cyclodextrin and without beta cyclodextrin. Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine) with beta cyclodextrin showed high level of fragrance intensity in combined dyeing and finishing than double stage method. Fragrance intensity was tested by human sensorial evaluation was found 10% after 70 days without washing and 30% retained after five time washing.

Keywords : Dyeing, finishing, Beta Cyclodextrin, Aroma finish, Microencapsulation, Emulsion.

Cite

Md. Anowar Hossain, (2015) “Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric” 6th all India Inter Engineering college academic meet-2015 and Science & Technology exhibition for a sustainable society, 26th April, 2015, JFT-05, Organised by Forum of Scientist, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), 15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street), Kolkata-7000087, India.

6TH ALL INDIA INTER ENGINEERING COLLEGE ACADEMIC MEET -2015

&

SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY EXHIBITION FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY

26TH APRIL, 2015

Organised by

FORUM OF SCIENTISTS, ENGINEERS & TECHNOLOGISTS (FOSET)

15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street), Kolkata – 700087

In Association with

MCKV Institute of Engineering

243 G.T.ROAD (N), LILUAH, HOWRAH-711 204

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This is to certify that Sri / Smt **MD. ANOWAR HOSSAIN** of **University of Calcutta** has presented a paper (Principal Author) titled **Integrated Dyeing and Cosmetic Finishing on Cotton Fabric** in **JUTE, TEXTILE & FIBRE TECHNOLOGY** Stream in the 6th ALL INDIA INTER ENGINEERING COLLEGE ACADEMIC MEET-2015 AND SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY EXHIBITION FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY organised by **Forum of Scientists, Engineers and Technologists (FOSET)** in association with **MCKV Institute of Engineering** on 26th April, 2015.

Date : 26.04.2015
Howrah

Dr. ASOK KUMAR
Principal
MCKV Institute of Engineering

Dr. ASHIK PAUL
General Secretary
FOSET

Prof. JAYA SIL
Chairperson,
Organising Committee

6th All India Inter Engineering College

ACADEMIC MEET

2015

&

SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY EXHIBITION
FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY

26th April, 2015

Organized by

**Forum of Scientists, Engineers
& Technologists (FOSET)**

On Association with

MCKV Institute of Engineering

Approved by the AICTE, affiliated to the WBUT and accredited
by the NBA for CSE and ECE department

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Guidelines for Model Exhibition (For 111 Students)

SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY EXHIBITION FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY

Introduction

"FOSET" is organizing a science & technological exhibition through models and exhibits as made by the skilled artisans to develop an understanding about the role of science & technology to meet the demand of the future towards sustainable development of the society.

The main objective to organize such exhibition first time in the arena of "Academic Meet", to envisage the engineers & technicians of the future would try to analyse all aspects of the role of science & technology for a sustainable world. This will enable the Target group to generate scientific and technological ideas for addressing various problems of the society. Scientific and technological ideas in this context may be referred to as innovative ways of doing things or development of new values through solutions that meet new requirement leading to sustainable production and uses.

The youth must be aware about how human society's unsustainable use of natural resources affects the quality of life and environment. The young engineers and technicians should identify where and how new researches and development in science & technology can bring sustainable development of the society.

This exhibition aims to cover areas

- 1) Mechanical & Production Engineering
- 2) Civil and Architecture Engineering
- 3) Electrical Engineering
- 4) Computer Science and Information Technology
- 5) Electronics

(Areas listed above are suggestive. The young engineers and technicians are free to choose any other area.)

Objectives

- To provide a forum to nurture science & technology
- To explore and encourage scientific and technological talent and creative thinking among youth.
- To develop an understanding about the role of science and technology towards sustainable development of the society.
- To analyse how science and technology have affected individuals, culture and society.
- To motivate the youth that science and technology are instrument for achieving self-reliance in socio-economic development.

Criteria for selection of the participants

1	Creative imagination	15%
2	Scientific thought and approach	15%
3	Originality & innovations in the model	15%
4	Technical Skill	15%
5	Economic (low cost / portability / durability)	15%
6	Presentation(demonstration & explanation)	15%
7	Educational Value	10%

Registration

Two participants per Model have to submit individually the attached Registration Form duly filled-in and signed and should be authorized by Head of the Department / Institute. The Registration Fee @ **Rs. 150.00 per head** is exempted for the **Principle / Presenting Model maker**.

Call For Papers

Papers are invited from Under Graduate & Post graduate students of Universities & Engineering Colleges on **Ready-to-Transfer Technologies and Field-level and Cost-effective Applications of Science and Technology**.

Call For Models

Models are invited from 111 students of different institutes on **Ready-to-Transfer Technology and Field-level and Cost-effective Applications of Skills in various department of Craftmanship**.

Awards

- Certificates will be awarded to all selected papers presenters and model makers.
- Cash Prizes of **Rs. 2,000/-** and **Rs. 1,000/-** will be awarded to the First & Second Prize winning papers respectively.
- Cash Prizes of **Rs. 2,000/-** will be awarded to the First Prize winning among the model makers.

Transport, Accommodation and other details

To and Fro Bus Fare / 2nd Class Train Fare will be reimbursed to each selected Out-station (beyond 100 Km from Kolkata) participant (One person per paper).

Tariff For Sponsorship / Advertisement

Collaborator	Rs. 50,000.00
Sponsorship of Exhibition	Rs. 25,000.00
Sponsorship of Stream	Rs. 15,000.00
Advertisement (Full Page)	Rs. 10,000.00
Sponsorship of prize	Rs. 5,000.00

Registration

At least one participant per Paper have to submit individually the attached Registration Form duly filled-in and signed and should be authorized by Head of the Department / Institute. The Registration Fee @ **Rs. 150.00 per head** is exempted for the **Principle / Presenting Author**.

Guidelines for Paper Submission (For UG & PG Students)

- The **Abstract** should generally not exceed **100 words** with maximum 5 key words.
- Submit one soft copy of the Manuscript (only through e-mail) and a CD containing the camera ready version of the paper at the time of presentation. The **Manuscript** should be within **maximum 4 pages in A4 paper**.
- The paper should be as per template of **Standard IEEE Conference format**, template can be downloaded from <http://www.fosetonline.org>.
- Please include black & white photographs only. The Paper should be ready-to-print in .doc format.

Abstract and Full Papers must be sent by e-mail to : foset@foset.in

Registration Form has to be sent by post/courier to FOSET office or e-mail the scanned copy of filled Registration.

TO Annash
8th ALL INDIA INTER ENGINEERING COL

ACADEMIC MEET - 2015

&

SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY EXHIBITION FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY

26th April, 2015

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About the Academic Meet

After an overwhelming response from the students of Engineering Colleges all over the country in the Academic Meets of 2010 to 2014, Forum of Scientists, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), a national level voluntary organization of professionals feels proud once again to organize the **6th All India Inter Engineering College Academic Meet - 2015 & Science & Technology Exhibition for a Sustainable Society on 26th April, 2015** in association with MCKV Institute of Engineering, West Bengal produces some of the finest talent in the field of Engineering and Technology through its systematic and well-organized network of colleges and universities. The Academic Meet is recognized as an effective platform for exploration and brainstorming by UG and PG students of engineering Colleges / Institutes / Universities in India, who have that positive inclination in translating their theoretical knowledge into technology for people. The event includes paper presentations before eminent experts in different fields. Avenues are also opened for presenting skill of craftsmanship for ITI students. Also, the two best papers of each stream would be awarded as a token of recognition and also would be published in a special issue of the journal **THOUGHT - A Socio Technical Round Up**. The **6th All India Inter Engineering College Academic Meet - 2015** will therefore look forward for an organizational expansion amongst the budding Engineers participating in the meet.

About FOSET's activities and Membership information and also for more detail about the **6th All India Inter Engineering College Academic Meet - 2015** please log on to our website: <http://www.fosetonline.org>

About MCKVIE

MCKVIE is a premiere co-ed Post Graduate Degree Engineering College in West Bengal. Approved by the All India Council for Technical Education, affiliated to the West Bengal University of Technology and accredited by the National Board of Accreditation for CSE and ECE departments, MCKVIE offers B. Tech, M. Tech and MCA degree courses. It has around 1500 students spread over six disciplines preparing to make their mark in the world.

Venue

MCKV Institute of Engineering
243 G. T. Road (N), Liluah Howrah - 711204
Phone: (033) 2654 9315/17, Fax: (033) 2654 9318
Website: <http://www.mckvie.edu.in>

Contact Details

Full Paper/s along with the filled-in Registration form to be E-mailed to the following address within due date:

The Convener,
6th All India Inter Engineering College Academic Meet - 2015 & Science & Technology Exhibition for a Sustainable Society Forum of Scientists, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET)
15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street),
New KMC Building (5th Floor), Kolkata - 700 087
Phone: 033 2252 9675, Fax: 033 2252 0521
Email: foset@foset.in, Web: <http://www.fosetonline.org>

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Prof. Sabhyasachi Sengupta, Chairman (E.R), AICTE & Former VC, WBUT
Prof. Subimal Sen, Former Chairman, WB Higher Education Council & President, FOSET
Sri Tapabrata Sanyal, Chief Consultant, National Jute Board
Sri Gouram Roy, E.D., CESC Ltd. & Vice President, FOSET
Mr. Kishan Kejriwal, Managing Trustee, MCKVIE
Sri Santanu Sengupta, MD, Westinghouse Saxy Ltd. & Vice President, FOSET
Prof. (Dr.) Asok Kumar, Principal & Professor - ECE, MCKVIE

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Important Dates

- ◆ Last date of submission of Full Text of Paper / Model Proposal : 3rd April, 2015
- ◆ Date of Notification of Acceptance : 10th April, 2015
- ◆ Last Date Submission of Registration : 15th April, 2015
- ◆ Last date for Submission of Camera Ready Paper : 15th April, 2015
- ◆ ACADEMIC MEET Paper Presentation : 26th April, 2015

Programme Details

DATE	SESSION	TIME
26 th April, 2015	Registration	10.00 AM to 11.00 AM
	Technical Session - I	11.00 AM to 01.30 PM
	Technical Session - II	02.30 PM to 05.00 PM
	Valedictory Session	05.30 PM to 06.30 PM
	Exhibition of Models	11.00 AM to 03.00 PM

Theme & Scope

STREAM	AREA
A. MECHANICAL ENGINEERING; INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING; MATERIAL SCIENCE & ENGINEERING	Mechanical Design, Thermal Engineering, Mechanics, Marine Engineering, Aerospace Engineering, Automotive Engineering, Computer Aided Engineering, Mechatronics; Production & related issues, Manufacturing Systems Engineering, Product and Quality Engineering, Economics and Work Design; Facility Engineering and Management, Test Technology & Maintenance Management, Process Engineering and Production Planning; Service Systems; Application of Optimization, Meta heuristic and Management Decision Techniques, Material Science and Advanced Application Materials; Nano-materials; Metallurgical Engineering
B. JUTE TEXTILE AND FIBER TECHNOLOGY	Technological Innovations in Jute & Textiles, Technical fabrics and textile, smart Textile, Application of Geo Textile in Engineering, Biotechnological Application of Geo Jute, Alternate fibers.
C. CIVIL ENGINEERING & ARCHITECTURE	Structural Engineering; Construction Engineering & Management; Geotechnical Engineering; Transportation Engineering; Water Resources Engineering; Architecture; Eco-City Planning, Smart city
D. ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING; INSTRUMENTATION ENGINEERING	Electrical Machines and Drives; Micro-Simulac; Power Systems and high voltage Engineering; Power Plant Engineering, Distribution and Transmission, Non-conventional Energy; control, instrumentation and measurement, biosensor and smart sensors. Orientation and Human Computer interface.
E. ELECTRONICS & COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING	Electronic Chip Design (VLSI), Microwave Engineering, Signal Processing, Communication Engineering, Embedded System, EMI & EMC - health & hazards, antenna design, communication & networking.
F. COMPUTER SCIENCE & ENGINEERING; INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY	Networking, Image Processing, Computer Architecture; Digital Technology, Information & Communication Technology, Application of Free & Open Source Software, Data Communication Technology, Cybernetics, E-Governance, DBMS & MISOS, Data mining.
G. CHEMICAL ENGINEERING; ENVIRONMENT ENGG.; PHARMACEUTICAL ENGINEERING	Chemical Process and Plant Design; Chemical Reaction Engineering, Catalysts development; Nanotechnology; Industrial Waste Treatment & Recovery; Environmental Process Design, Global Warming, Pharmaceuticals, Pharmaceutical Bio-Technology & Industrial Microbiology, Pharmaceutical Bio-Technology & Industrial Microbiology
H. BIO-TECHNOLOGY; FOOD TECHNOLOGY; AGRICULTURAL ENGG.	Biotechnology; Molecular and Microbial Biotechnology; Genetic Engineering; Biochemistry; Food Product and Process Design; Food Innovation and Management; Bioengineering; Bioinformatics; Agricultural Product Production and processing of agricultural products; Agricultural Equipment and Technology.

**6th ALL INDIA INTER ENGINEERING COLLEGE ACADEMIC MEET – 2015
& SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY EXHIBITION FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY**

Organised by FORUM OF SCIENTISTS, ENGINEERS & TECHNOLOGISTS (FOSET)

AT MCKV INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING

26TH APRIL, 2015

INAUGURAL PROGRAMME

Welcome Address	Prof (Dr) Jaya Sil Chairperson, Organising Committee	11.00 AM
Guest of Honour	Sri Kishan Kumar Kejriwal Managing Trustee, MCKVIE	11.05 AM
Guest of Honour	Prof (Dr) Parasar Bandopadhyay Director, MCKVIE	11.10 AM
Chief Guest	Sri Tapobrata Sanyal Chief Consultant, National Jute Board	11.15 AM
Presidential Address	Prof (Dr) Subimal Sen President, FOSET	11.25 AM
Inaugural Address	Prof (Dr) Parijat De Director of Technical Education & Training, Govt. of WB	11.30 AM
Vote of Thanks	Prof (Dr) Asok Kumar Principal, MCKVIE	11.40 AM

VALIDATORY SESSION

Introductory Address	Prof (Dr) Jaya Sil Chairperson, Organising Committee	04.45 PM
Validatory Address	Prof (Dr) Nil Ratan Bandopadhyay IEST, Sibpore	04.50 PM
Guest of Honour	Prof (Dr) Asok Kumar Principal, MCKV IE	05.00 PM
Certificate & Prize Award		05.05 PM to 05.30 PM

“Integrated Dyeing and Cosmetic Finishing on Cotton Fabric”

By

Md. Anowar Hossain

M.Tech. Student

Under the Guidance of

Professor (Dr.) A.K. Samanta

Professor and Head of the Department

Department of Jute and Fibre technology

Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta

Objectives of the Present Work

Feasibility of Single stage dyeing and multifinishing comparing with conventional double stage dyeing and finishing

Durable fragrance finishing for cotton textiles which may be an alternative invention of artificial perfume.

Effective use of beta cyclodextrin as dyeing bath auxiliaries as well as fragrance finishing also.

Why Integration in Dyeing and Finishing

One Stage Reducing

Time saving

Water saving and minimising WTP cost

Environment –friendly

Drying Cost

Low vapour-gas-emission

Heat energy saving

Low labour cost

Very low Effluent Treatment cost

Why Cosmetic Finishing on Textile

Relaxation
Sensuality
Exhilaration
Happiness
Well being

Stress reducing
High blood pressure reducing
Psychological & emotional improvement

Demands of Fragrance in Global Market

Fragrances Industry

Global Market for Flavors
2006 (US\$ Million)

- W Europe
- E Europe
- N America
- S America
- Asia-Pacific
- Middle East & Africa

Introduction on Cotton fibre

Schematic Structure of cotton fibre

Cotton Fibre

Repeat unit cellulose in cotton fibre

Introduction on Reactive dyes and Dyeing

Schematic Structure of Reactive Dye

Structure of Reactive Dye

Reaction between reactive dye and cellulose

Characteristics of Reactive dye:

Chromogenic part of the reactive dye

Reactive Groups

Monochlorotriazine ring.

Sulphonate ($-SO_3Na$) Group

Literature review
on
Simultaneous dyeing and finishing

Benefit of combined dyeing and finishing

Specialized section	Fuel	Electricity	Total	Percentage share
				in total
Fiber production	32551	21498	54049	21.0
Spinning	3224	44262	47480	18.4
Twisting	219	1660	1879	0.7
Textured yarn production	120	1543	1663	0.6
Weaving	4467	24848	29315	11.4
Knitting	4059	11709	15858	6.1
Conventional Dyeing and subsequent finishing in separate two step process (for both knitted and woven fabrics)				
	37661	28412	66073	25.0
Clothing manufacturing	8240	15420	23660	9.2
Others	5959	12000	17959	7.0
Total	96500	161442	257942	100.0

Energy consumption (in million Yen*) in the Japanese textile industry¹

Simultaneous dyeing and finishing

Bleached jute, Reactive dyes, DMDHEU

Bleached jute fabric, acid dye, DMDHEU

Significant improvement found:

Highly increased K/S value

Good levelness of dyeing

Higher dry crease recovery angle

Improved strength for beta Cyclodextrin

Dye fixation

Surface colour strength

Washing, rubbing & Light fastness

Ref-1: M Kamaluddin, M E Molla, S M B Rahman, M A K Azad, H M ZakirHossain &M M U Jubayer, J Bio Sci, 7(1) (2007)68

Ref-2: N C Pan, S N Chattopadhyay & A Day, Colourage, 4(1996) 32-36.

Ref-3: A K Samanta, D Singhee & K K Mahalanabis ,IE (I) Journal, 88(2) (2008) 17-25.

Ref-4: Improvement of ink jet printing performance using beta cyclodextrin on cotton fabric, Textile research journal, Manuscript ID TRJ-15-0179

Literature review
on
Aroma finishing

Fragrance and its function

Jasmine

Pachouli

Rose

Fragrance versus human sensory organs

By human olfactory neurons, only a few molecules are necessary for us to experience or identify scents.

Cyclodextrin

Corn is the raw material that provides the starch for cyclodextrin production

Structure of Dextrin

α , β & γ Cyclodextrin for microencapsulation

Figure: Structure of α -cyclodextrin, β -cyclodextrin, γ -cyclodextrin

Ref: David Rowe, WILEY publications, Chemistry and technology of flavours and fragrances.

α, β & γ Cyclodextrin for microencapsulation

Physicochemical properties	Alfa	Beta	Gama	Lamda
No of glycopyranose units	6	7	8	9
Central cavity diameter	4.7-5.3	6.0-6.5	7.5-8.3	10.3-11.2
Water solubility at 25°C	14.5	1.85	23.2	8.19
Molecular weight	972	1135	1297	1459

Ref: Development of cosmetic textiles using microencapsulation technology, S.Y. cheng, C.W.M. Yuen, C.W. Kan and K.K.L. Cheuk, RJTA Vol.12 (4) 2008.

Mechanism of microencapsulation

Natural Example of Microencapsulation

Why Microencapsulation

1. Controlled release or sustained release.
2. Protection of core content
3. Prevent interaction with other chemicals in the system
4. Protect active component from physical damage.

Ref: Development of cosmetic textiles using microencapsulation technology, S. Y. cheng, C.W.M. Yuen, C.W. Kan and K.K.L. Cheuk, RJTA Vol.12 (4) 2008.

Materials and Method

Chemical Selection

Alcohol: Distilled water=1:3

Citric acid-6%, Sodium hypophosphite-6%

Beta Cyclodextrin 1-50%

Sodium carbonate for alkaline pH

Percentage of dyestuff was kept constant & three types of fragrance chemical was trialed to get better performance in double stage as well as combined dyeing and finishing.

References

Aromachology and its application in the textile field, C.X. Wang, Sh.L.Chen, email: Wangchaoxia@sohu.com, College of textile and garments, Southern Yangtze University, College of chemistry and Chemical engineering, Donghua University, Shanghai 200051, P.R. China

Imparting antimicrobial and fragrance finish on cotton using chitosan with silicon softner, Anjali Karolia, Snehal Mendapara, Indian journal of fibre and textile science, Volume-32, March-2007, PP-99-104.

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Synthesis of reactive fragranced entities and their application to cotton textiles, D.P. Chattopadhyay, Shweta, J.Doctor, Textiles and light industrial science and technology, Volume-2, Issue-2, April-2013.

Microencapsulation Methods:

Ref: Development of cosmetic textiles using microencapsulation technology, S. Y. cheng, C.W.M. Yuen, C.W. Kan and K.K.L. Cheuk, RJTA Vol.12 (4) 2008.

Double stage dyeing and Finishing machine **Single stage dyeing and finishing machine**

**Effect of beta cyclodextrin for microencapsulation
in combined dyeing and finishing comparing with dextrin and DMDHEU**

An Emulsifier was prepared by Polyethylene glycol & Distilled water (1:3)

Types of chemical	Conc.	R. Lemon yellow –CN	Synthetic Fragrance	Citric Acid	Sodium Hypophospite	Emulsifier	Sodium Carbonate
Beta Cyclodextrin	5%	1%	1%	10%	6%	77%	for ph 10-11
	10%	1%	1%	10%	6%	72%	for ph 10-11
	15%	1%	1%	10%	6%	67%	for ph 10-11
Dextrin	5%	1%	1%	10%	6%	77%	for ph 10-11
	10%	1%	1%	10%	6%	72%	for ph 10-11
	15%	1%	1%	10%	6%	67%	for ph 10-11
DMDHEU	5%	1%	1%	10%	6%	77%	for ph 10-11
	10%	1%	1%	10%	6%	72%	for ph 10-11
	15%	1%	1%	10%	6%	67%	for ph 10-11

Effect of fragrance and beta cyclodextrin in combined dyeing and finishing							
An Emulsifier was prepared by Polyethylene glycol & Distilled water (1:3) ⁽²²⁾							
Types of fragrance	Fragrance conc.	Dye-Lemon yellow CN	Beta Cyclodextrin	Emulsifier	Citric Acid	Sodium hypophosphate	Sodium Carbonate
Synthetic (Jasmine)	1%	1%	10%	72%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	2%	1%	10%	71%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	3%	1%	10%	70%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
Rose oil	1%	1%	10%	72%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	2%	1%	10%	71%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	3%	1%	10%	70%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
Pachouli oil	1%	1%	10%	72%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	2%	1%	10%	71%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	3%	1%	10%	70%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine)	1%	1%	0%	72%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	2%	1%	0%	71%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	3%	1%	0%	70%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
Rose oil	1%	1%	0%	72%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	2%	1%	0%	71%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	3%	1%	0%	70%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
Pachouli oil	1%	1%	0%	72%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	2%	1%	0%	71%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	3%	1%	0%	70%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11

Probable reaction in combined dyeing and finishing where monochlorotriazinyl group of reactive dye is making covalent bond with beta cyclodextrin and OH group of cotton fibre:

Major Benefit of combined dyeing and finishing:

Increasing the color strength (K/S) (**Shown in table 3**)

Controlled release of fragrance (**shown in table-04 & 5**)

Dry crease recovery angle (**Shown in table 3**)

Hydrolysis rate of dyestuff is minimizing and wastage rate of dyestuff is very minor.

Soft hand feel of fabric

Time, heat energy & water saving

low vapour-gas-emission

Low labour cost

Environment –friendly

Alternative of DMDHEU

Effect of physical properties, dyeing properties and finishing properties of Double stage dyeing and finishing as well as Combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric:

Treatments	T. strength (N/M)Wp & Wf	(+) in strength	(-) in strength	K/S value	Color fastness To wash	Light fastness	Dry crease Angle
Bleached untreated cotton fabric	0.278, 0.208		.002,.003	.0542	-	-	162
Dyed cotton fabric with conventional method	.270,.200		.008,.008	3.001	3	3	180
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and beta cyclodextrin	.276, .205		.008, .013	2.898	4	4	256
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and without beta cyclodextrin	.270,.195		.004,.009	2.999	2	2	200
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and dexrin instead of B-CD	.274,.199		.018,.013	2.695	2	2	230
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and DMDHEU instead of B-CD	.260,.195		-	2.565	2	2	250
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and beta cyclodextrin	.290, .280	.012, .072	.003, .008	3.239	3	3	264
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and without beta cyclodextrin	.275,.200	0	0	3.338	2	2	190
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and dexrin instead of B-CD	.278,.208		.009,.010	2.765	2	2	220
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and DMDHEU instead of B-CD	.269,.198		.002,.003	2.865	2	2	240

Data Table-03

Fragrance grading scale 0-100%, sensorial evaluation after number of days without washing

Types of fragrance	Fragrance concentration	Beta Cyclodextrin	First days	10th days	20th days	30 th days	40th days	50th days	60th days	70th days	80th days
Synthetic (Jasmine)	1%	10%	90%	80%	80%	70%	70%	30%	20%	10%	0%
	2%	10%	95%	85%	85%	80%	70%	40%	20%	10%	0%
	3%	10%	95%	85%	85%	80%	70%	40%	20%	10%	0%
Rose oil	1%	10%	50%	40%	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	55%	40%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	10%	55%	40%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	10%	85%	70%	40%	10%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	90%	70%	40%	10%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	10%	90%	70%	40%	10%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine)	1%	0%	90%	70%	50%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	90%	70%	50%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	90%	70%	50%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Rose oil	1%	0%	90%	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	90%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	90%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	0%	90%	40%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	90%	40%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	90%	40%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Data Table-04

Fragrance grading scale 0-100%, human sensorial evaluation after number of washing

Types of fragrance	Fragrance conc.	B. Cyclodextrin	Before washing	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth
Synthetic (Jasmine)	1%	10%	90%	90%	80%	60%	50%	30%
	2%	10%	95%	90%	80%	70%	60%	40%
	3%	10%	95%	90%	80%	70%	60%	40%
Rose oil	1%	10%	50%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	55%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	10%	55%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	10%	85%	50%	20%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	90%	60%	30%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	10%	90%	60%	30%	0%	0%	0%
Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine)	1%	0%	90%	60%	40%	10%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	95%	70%	90%	10%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	95%	70%	90%	10%	0%	0%
Rose oil	1%	0%	40%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	45%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	45%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	0%	85%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Data Table-05

**Expected Application Areas
of
Fragrance finishing on Textile Substrates**

Bed Room curtains

Windows curtains

Sofa cover

Bed cover

Pillow cover

Sports wear

Exercise wear

Socks

Gloves

Ties

Handkerchief

Ladies inner

Fragrance finishing On Garments products

Womens
Product ID#1026

Garments video.flv
Womens
Product ID#1027

Womens
Product ID#1028

Conclusion

Process Minimisation = Cost Minimisation

Chemical Minimisation = Cost Minimisation

Technical finishing = Value added Product

Process minimisation + Chemical Minimisation = Ecofriendly Tech = Healthy life

Sample Exhibition

And

Garments video.flv

Question and Answering Session

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Never forget how to dream

Thank you